

The SIRD Epidemic Model with Markov and Semi-Markov Assumptions

El modelo epidémico SIRD con supuestos de Markov y semi-Markov

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Abstract

[Objective] This study aims to complement the shortcomings of the Markov model in modeling the spread of infectious diseases by adding the assumption of sojourn time in each state, called the semi-Markov model. The semi-Markov process does not have the limitations of the Markov model, where reality shows that the sojourn time distribution function in a continuous-time semi-Markov process can take any form. **[Materials and Methods]** There are two ways to define a multi-state model based on semi-Markov assumptions: the sojourn time approach and the transition intensity function approach. This study uses the sojourn time method to determine the appropriate distribution for each state transition. Sojourn time distribution comprises the Exponential distribution and the Weibull distribution. The model estimate employs maximum likelihood methods based on the sojourn time approach. **[Results]** The semi-Markov assumption is applied to the SIRD epidemic model, which consists of four states: susceptible, infected, recovered, and deceased, using COVID-19 data from the Special Region of Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Comparing the AIC values of the two models revealed that the semi-Markov model produced superior results than the Markov model. Under the semi-Markov model, the Weibull distribution makes dynamic probabilities with a faster rate of decline and smaller variance. **[Conclusion]** The SIRD epidemic model with a semi-Markov assumption can overcome the weaknesses of the Markov assumption. So to model the spread of infectious diseases, it is better to pay attention to the sojourn time in one state before transitioning to another.

Keywords: semi-Markov; sojourn time; SIRD model; maximum likelihood; COVID-19.

Resumen

[Objetivo] Este estudio tiene como objetivo complementar las deficiencias del modelo de Markov en el modelado de la propagación de enfermedades infecciosas al agregar la suposición del tiempo de permanencia en cada estado, llamado modelo semi-Markov. El proceso de semi-Markov no tiene las limitaciones del modelo de Markov, donde la realidad muestra que la función de distribución del tiempo de permanencia en un proceso de semi-Markov de tiempo continuo puede tomar cualquier forma. **[Materiales y métodos]** Hay dos formas de definir un modelo multiestado basado en suposiciones semi-Markov: el enfoque del tiempo de permanencia y el enfoque de la función de intensidad de transición. Este estudio utiliza el método de tiempo de permanencia para determinar la distribución adecuada para cada transición de estado. La distribución del tiempo de estancia

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comprende la distribución Exponencial y la distribución Weibull. La estimación del modelo emplea métodos de máxima verosimilitud basados en el enfoque del tiempo de permanencia. **[Resultados]** El supuesto semi-Markov se aplica al modelo epidémico SIRD, que consta de cuatro estados: susceptible, infectado, recuperado y fallecido, utilizando datos de COVID-19 de la Región Especial de Yogyakarta, Indonesia. La comparación de los valores AIC de los dos modelos reveló que el modelo semi-Markov produjo resultados superiores que el modelo Markov. Bajo el modelo semi-Markov, la distribución de Weibull genera probabilidades dinámicas con una tasa de declive más rápida y una varianza más pequeña. **[Conclusión]** El modelo epidémico SIRD con un supuesto de semi-Markov puede superar las debilidades del supuesto de Markov. Entonces, para modelar la propagación de enfermedades infecciosas, es mejor prestar atención al tiempo de permanencia en un estado antes de pasar a otro.

Keywords: semi-Markov; tiempo de estancia; modelo SIRD; máxima verosimilitud; COVID-19.

Introduction

Modeling the spread of infectious diseases has been developed after the outbreak of COVID-19, which has been troubling the lives of the world's population for almost two years. The epidemic model starts from the simplest involving three states, namely the SIR (Susceptible, Infected, Recovered) model, to the addition of states such as deceased, vaccinated, and even exposed. In our research in Zuhairoh, *et al.* (2022) we have discussed the discrete-time SVIRS model using Markov assumptions. Other studies using the Markov model have also been carried out by Hsieh *et al.* (2002); Cohen and Reza (2011); Hubbard and Zhou (2011); Zhang *et al.* (2019).

Typically, the state space of a Markov chain is finite. The likelihood of transitioning to any state is contingent on the current condition and time. This phenomenon can be observed in disease modeling, where the probability of people becoming sick at the earliest possible moment relies on the number of people who are currently diseased. To forecast future events, the researcher simply needs information on current events; extra information about the past is sufficient. This attribute is known as the Markov property or the memoryless property. The memoryless nature of text makes Markov chains an indispensable modeling tool for natural events.

Even though the Markov model has been widely used in various fields, this model still needs to improve. For example, in the context of discrete time, the transition time of the Markov model is not stochastic, whereas, in continuous time, the intensity of the transition is constant. Of course, this simplifies a huge problem, so it is appropriate that the Markov model still has to be perfected. One way to do this is to provide additional assumptions to the Markov model, namely that apart from depending on the current state, the intensity and probability of the transition are also affected by the time spent by the system in the current state since the last transition to that state as written by Foucher *et al.* (2005). Foucher *et al.* (2005) emphasizes the comparison of the sojourn time distributions used. As a result, the Markov nature will be brought to a new definition, namely the semi-Markov process.

The semi-Markov process is a type of stochastic process. It can be analogous to a combination of two other stochastic processes: the Markov chain and the renewal process. The semi-Markov process does not have the limitations that are lacking in the Markov model, where the reality shows that the distribution function of the transition intensity in a continuous-time semi-Markov process can be of any shape. In contrast, in the case of

discrete-time, the semi-Markov process transition time is stochastic in that it makes discrete-time semi-Markov processes closer to reality. Research on the semi-Markov model has been carried out by Janssen and Manca (2001); Asanjarani *et al.* (2021). In modeling infectious diseases, there is still little research that takes into account how long it takes to be in a specific state, for example, how long does a person live until he is infected with a disease, how long does it take to recover or how long does it take to treat a person until he dies as has been done by Mengesha *et al.* (2018) on HIV AIDS.

In general, two approaches can be used to define a semi-Markov model: the sojourn time approach and the transition intensity function approach (Asanjarani *et al.*, 2021). In this paper, we will only use the sojourn time distribution to determine the transition probabilities between states, where each transition can use a different sojourn time distribution depending on the suitability of the data in a particular distribution. The method used is the maximum estimation of likelihood. Each transition is made a histogram plot, and then the suitability of the distribution used is seen. Then tested for the three distributions used in this study: the Exponential distribution, Gamma distribution, and Weibull distribution. This aims to discover that multi-state models with semi-Markov assumptions can use different distributions in each state transition.

Section 1 of this article describes several studies using Markov assumptions and the rationale for using semi-Markov to model the spread of infectious diseases. We then explain the novelty of our research and its differences from previous studies. Section 2 discusses the SIRD epidemic model and how to find the estimated transition parameters. Section 3 discusses the semi-Markov process with the sojourn time approach. In section 4, we apply the SIRD epidemic model with COVID-19 data using Markov and semi-Markov assumptions. Finally, section 5 contains conclusions.

SIRD Epidemic Model

Figure 1. *SIRD Epidemic Model.*

The model formed based on assumptions such as variables and parameters in Figure 1 can be expressed mathematically by using the following system of equations.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS(w)}{dw} &= -\frac{\beta S(w)I(w)}{N} + o(\Delta w) \\ \frac{dI(w)}{dw} &= \frac{\beta S(w)I(w)}{N} - \theta I(w) - \alpha I(w) + o(\Delta w) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dR(w)}{dw} &= \theta I(w) + o(\Delta w) \\ \frac{dD(w)}{dw} &= \alpha I(w) + o(\Delta w)\end{aligned}$$

The transition probability that occurs between states in Figure 1 is written as follows.

$$p_{12}(\Delta w) = \frac{\beta si}{N} \Delta w + o(\Delta w) \quad (1)$$

$$p_{23}(\Delta w) = \theta i \Delta w + o(\Delta w) \quad (2)$$

$$p_{24}(\Delta w) = \alpha i \Delta w + o(\Delta w) \quad (3)$$

$$p_{kk}(\Delta w) = 1 - \left(\frac{\beta si}{N} + \theta i + \alpha i \right) \Delta w + o(\Delta w) \quad (4)$$

Equation (1) shows the probability of transition from susceptible to infected, Equation (2) shows the probability of transition from being infected to cured, Equation (3) shows the probability of transition from infected to dead, and Equation (4) denotes the probability of staying in a certain state where $k = 1, 2, 3$.

The parameters used in the Equation (1-4) will be estimated using the maximum likelihood method. In the compartment model, parameter values are usually derived based on the differential equations that have been made based on the epidemic model, while in this study based on the intensity of the transition with an exponential distribution of sojourn times.

The SIRD epidemic model in continuous time has a transition probability of $(p_{(s,i,r) \rightarrow (s+x,i+y,r+z)}(\Delta w))$ is given as following.

$$p(\Delta w) = \begin{cases} \frac{\beta}{N} si \Delta w + o(\Delta w), & (x, y, z) = (-1, 1, 0) \\ \theta i \Delta w + o(\Delta w), & (x, y, z) = (0, -1, 1) \\ \alpha i \Delta w + o(\Delta w), & (x, y, z) = (0, -1, 0) \\ 1 - \left(\frac{\beta si}{N} + \theta i + \alpha i \right) \Delta w + o(\Delta w), & (x, y, z) = (0, 0, 0) \\ o(\Delta w), & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Probability of transition from state (s, i, r) to state $(s + x, i + y, r + z)$, expressed by the Equation (5). The number of individual groups S, I, R , and D can be determined at any given time using the Equation (5), and their initial values are given first.

The parameters used in the Equation (1-4) will be estimated using the maximum likelihood method. In the compartment model, parameter values are usually derived based on differential equations that have been made based on the epidemic model, whereas in this study based on the intensity of the transition with exponential distribution of sojourn times.

According to the continuous-time SIRD epidemic model with transition probabilities in Equation (5), it is possible to estimate the parameters β, θ , and α by the maximum likelihood method. The total number of transitions included in this process is k . At any given instant in time, each observation takes place within the time (w_0, w) , where $w \geq w_k$, and there are no transitions between the time intervals (w_k, w) at any point in time.

Theorem 1. The estimated value of each parameter from the continuous time SIRD epidemic model can be obtained by the maximum likelihood method which is written as follows.

1. Infection rate

$$\hat{\beta} = \frac{a}{\sum_{i=0}^k \left[\frac{S(w_i)I(w_i)W_i}{N} \right]} \quad (6)$$

2. Recovery rate

$$\hat{\theta} = \frac{b}{\sum_{i=0}^k [I(w_i)W_i]} \quad (7)$$

3. Mortality rate

$$\hat{\alpha} = \frac{c}{\sum_{i=0}^k [I(w_i)W_i]} \quad (8)$$

where a is the transition from susceptible state to infected, b transition from infected state to recovered, c transition from infected to deceased state.

Proof. The likelihood function of the continuous-time SIRD epidemic model is as follows.

$$L(\beta, \theta, \alpha) = \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} (\lambda_{s_i} e^{-\lambda_{s_i} W_i}) (p_{s_i \rightarrow s_{i+1}}) e^{-\lambda_{s_k} (w - \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} W_i)} \quad (9)$$

where $\lambda_{s_i} e^{-\lambda_{s_i} W_i}$ is the probability of sojourn of W_i in state s_i , $p_{s_i \rightarrow s_{i+1}}$ is the probability of transition from state s_i to s_{i+1} and $e^{-\lambda_{s_k} (w - \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} W_i)}$ is the probability that no additional transitions occur after time s_k to time w . We observe that $\sum_{i=0}^{k-1} W_i = w_k$. Suppose $w - w_k = W_k$, so

$$e^{-\lambda_{s_k} (w - \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} W_i)} = e^{-\lambda_{s_k} (W_k)}$$

Consequently, the equation (9) can be written as follows.

$$L(\beta, \theta, \alpha) = e^{-\lambda_{s_k} (W_k)} \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} (\lambda_{s_i} e^{-\lambda_{s_i} W_i}) (p_{s_i \rightarrow s_{i+1}}) \quad (10)$$

Let $(w_{\beta_1}, w_{\beta_2}, \dots, w_{\beta_\alpha})$ be the set of times when the transition from (s, i, r) to $(s - 1, i + 1, r)$, $(w_{\theta_1}, w_{\theta_2}, \dots, w_{\theta_b})$ is the set of times when the transition from (s, i, r) to $(s, i - 1, r + 1)$, and $(w_{\alpha_1}, w_{\alpha_2}, \dots, w_{\alpha_c})$ is the set of times when the transition from (s, i, r) to $(s, i - 1, r)$.

Susceptible to Infected $((s, i, r) \rightarrow (s - 1, i + 1, r))$ transition probability is

$$p_{12} = \frac{\frac{\beta si}{N}}{\frac{\beta si}{N} + \alpha i + \theta i} \quad (11)$$

Infected to recovered $((s, i, r) \rightarrow (s, i - 1, r + 1))$ transition probability is

$$p_{23} = \frac{\theta i}{\frac{\beta si}{N} + \theta i} \quad (12)$$

infected to deceased $((s, i, r) \rightarrow (s, i - 1, r))$ transition probability is

$$p_{24} = \frac{\alpha i}{\frac{\beta si}{N} + \alpha i} \quad (13)$$

After obtaining the equation for each transition probability between states, the next step is to construct the likelihood function and then find the logarithm of the likelihood function and the partial derivatives of the logarithm of the likelihood function for each parameter used. We divide the transition probabilities between states, $p_{s_i \rightarrow s_{i+1}}$, into three

possible transition cases, namely the first from a susceptible state to being infected, infected to cured, and infected to dead. The likelihood function changed to

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} (\lambda_{s_i} e^{-\lambda_{s_i} W_i}) (p_{s_i \rightarrow s_{i+1}}) &= \left[\prod_{u=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta_a}} \left(\frac{\beta S(u)I(u)}{N} + \theta I(u) + \alpha I(u) \right) \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\beta S(u)I(u)}{N} + \theta I(u) + \alpha I(u) \right) W_u \right) \left(\frac{\frac{\beta S(u)I(u)}{N}}{\frac{\beta S(u)I(u)}{N} + \theta I(u) + \alpha I(u)} \right) \right] \times \\ &\left[\prod_{v=w_{\theta_1}}^{w_{\theta_b}} \left(\eta S(v) + \frac{\beta S(v)I(v)}{N} + \theta I(v) + \alpha I(v) \right) \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\beta S(v)I(v)}{N} + \theta I(v) + \alpha I(v) \right) W_v \right) \left(\frac{\theta I(v)}{\frac{\beta S(v)I(v)}{N} + \theta I(v) + \alpha I(v)} \right) \right] \times \\ &\left[\prod_{t=w_{\alpha_1}}^{w_{\alpha_c}} \left(\frac{\beta S(t)I(t)}{N} + \theta I(t) + \alpha I(t) \right) \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\beta S(t)I(t)}{N} + \theta I(t) + \alpha I(t) \right) W_t \right) \left(\frac{\alpha I(t)}{\frac{\beta S(t)I(t)}{N} + \theta I(t) + \alpha I(t)} \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, it can be simplified into the following equation.

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} (\lambda_{s_i} e^{-\lambda_{s_i} W_i}) (p_{s_i \rightarrow s_{i+1}}) &= \left[\prod_{u=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta_a}} \frac{\beta S(u)I(u)}{N} \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\beta S(u)I(u)}{N} \right) - \theta I(u) - \alpha I(u) \right) W_u \right] \times \\ &\left[\prod_{v=w_{\theta_1}}^{w_{\theta_b}} \theta I(v) \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\beta S(v)I(v)}{N} \right) - \theta I(v) - \alpha I(v) \right) W_v \right] \times \\ &\left[\prod_{t=w_{\alpha_1}}^{w_{\alpha_c}} \alpha I(t) \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\beta S(t)I(t)}{N} \right) - \theta I(t) - \alpha I(t) \right) W_t \right] \end{aligned}$$

This is the expression for the likelihood function.

$$\begin{aligned} L(\beta, \theta, \alpha) &= \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\beta S(w_k)I(w_k)}{N} + \theta I(w_k) + \alpha I(w_k) \right) W_k \right) \times \\ &\prod_{u=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta_a}} \left[\frac{\beta S(u)I(u)}{N} \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\beta S(u)I(u)}{N} + \theta I(u) + \alpha I(u) \right) W_u \right) \right] \times \\ &\prod_{v=w_{\theta_1}}^{w_{\theta_b}} \left[\theta I(v) \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\beta S(v)I(v)}{N} + \theta I(v) + \alpha I(v) \right) W_v \right) \right] \times \\ &\prod_{t=w_{\alpha_1}}^{w_{\alpha_c}} \left[\alpha I(t) \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\beta S(t)I(t)}{N} + \theta I(t) + \alpha I(t) \right) W_t \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

It is obtained by providing the logarithm of the likelihood function.

$$\begin{aligned} \log L(\beta, \theta, \alpha) &= - \left(\frac{\beta S(w_k)I(w_k)}{N} + \theta I(w_k) + \alpha I(w_k) \right) W_k + \sum_{u=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta_a}} \left[\log \left(\frac{\beta S(u)I(u)}{N} \right) - \left(\frac{\beta S(u)I(u)}{N} + \theta I(u) + \alpha I(u) \right) W_u \right] \\ &+ \sum_{v=w_{\theta_1}}^{w_{\theta_b}} \left[\log(\theta I(v)) - \left(\frac{\beta S(v)I(v)}{N} + \theta I(v) + \alpha I(v) \right) W_v \right] \\ &+ \sum_{t=w_{\alpha_1}}^{w_{\alpha_c}} \left[\log(\alpha I(t)) - \left(\frac{\beta S(t)I(t)}{N} + \theta I(t) + \alpha I(t) \right) W_t \right] \end{aligned}$$

We then obtain β by taking the partial derivative of the logarithm of the probability function with respect to β .

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \log L(\beta, \theta, \alpha)}{\partial \beta} &= - \left[\frac{S(w_k)I(w_k)}{N} \right] W_k + \sum_{u=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta_a}} \left[\frac{1}{\beta} - \left(\frac{S(u)I(u)}{N} \right) W_u \right] - \\ &\sum_{v=w_{\theta_1}}^{w_{\theta_b}} \left[\left(\frac{S(v)I(v)}{N} \right) W_v \right] - \sum_{t=w_{\alpha_1}}^{w_{\alpha_c}} \left[\left(\frac{S(t)I(t)}{N} \right) W_t \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= - \left[\frac{S(w_k)I(w_k)}{N} \right] W_k + \sum_{u=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta a}} \left(\frac{1}{\beta} \right) - \\
&\quad \left(\sum_{u=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta a}} \left[\left(\frac{S(u)I(u)}{N} \right) W_u \right] + \sum_{u=w_{\theta_1}}^{w_{\theta b}} \left[\left(\frac{S(v)I(v)}{N} \right) W_v \right] + \right. \\
&\quad \left. \sum_{t=w_{\alpha_1}}^{w_{\alpha c}} \left[\left(\frac{S(t)I(t)}{N} \right) W_t \right] \right) \\
&= - \left[\frac{S(w_k)I(w_k)}{N} \right] W_k + \sum_{v=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta a}} \left(\frac{1}{\beta} \right) - \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \left[\left(\frac{S(w_i)I(w_i)}{N} \right) W_i \right] \\
&= \frac{b}{\beta} - \sum_{i=0}^k \left[\left(\frac{S(w_i)I(w_i)}{N} \right) W_i \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Same applies to the θ parameter

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \log L(\beta, \theta, \alpha)}{\partial \theta} &= -I(w_k)W_k + \sum_{v=w_{\theta_1}}^{w_{\theta b}} \left[\frac{1}{\theta} - (I(v))W_v \right] - \sum_{u=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta a}} [I(u)W_u] - \\
&\quad \sum_{t=w_{\alpha_1}}^{w_{\alpha c}} [I(t)W_t] \\
&= -I(w_k)W_k + \sum_{v=w_{\theta_1}}^{w_{\theta b}} \left(\frac{1}{\theta} \right) - \left(\sum_{u=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta a}} [I(u)W_u] + \sum_{t=w_{\alpha_1}}^{w_{\alpha c}} [I(t)W_t] \right) \\
&= -I(w_k)W_k + \sum_{v=w_{\theta_1}}^{w_{\theta b}} \left(\frac{1}{\theta} \right) - \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} [I(w_i)W_i] \\
&= \frac{b}{\theta} - \sum_{i=0}^n [I(w_i)W_i]
\end{aligned}$$

Same applies to the α parameter

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \log L(\beta, \theta, \alpha)}{\partial \alpha} &= -I(w_k)W_k + \sum_{t=w_{\alpha_1}}^{w_{\alpha c}} \left[\frac{1}{\alpha} - (I(t))W_t \right] - \sum_{u=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta a}} [I(u)W_u] - \\
&\quad \sum_{v=w_{\theta_1}}^{w_{\theta b}} [I(v)W_v] \\
&= -I(w_k)W_k + \sum_{t=w_{\alpha_1}}^{w_{\alpha c}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha} \right) - \left(\sum_{u=w_{\beta_1}}^{w_{\beta a}} [I(u)W_u] + \sum_{v=w_{\theta_1}}^{w_{\theta b}} [I(v)W_v] \right) \\
&= -I(w_k)W_k + \sum_{t=w_{\alpha_1}}^{w_{\alpha c}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha} \right) - \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} [I(w_i)W_i] \\
&= \frac{c}{\alpha} - \sum_{i=0}^k [I(w_i)W_i]
\end{aligned}$$

The value of $\hat{\beta}$ that corresponds to the maximum probability estimate is the value of β in such a way that

$$\frac{\partial \log L(\beta, \theta, \alpha)}{\partial \beta} = 0$$

Hence, obtained

$$\hat{\beta} = \frac{a}{\sum_{i=0}^k \left[\frac{S(w_i)I(w_i)W_i}{N} \right]}$$

in the same way the parameter values are obtained θ , and α . ■

If using real data, parameter values can be determined based on Equations (6-8).

The Sojourn Time Approach in a Semi-Markov Process

One way to define a semi-Markov process is to use a homogeneous Markov chain $\{Z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ in state $\{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ where the transition probability from state k to state l for $k \neq l$ is p_{kl} which can be written as (Asanjarani *et al.*, 2021),

$$p_{kl} = \Pr(Z_n = l | Z_{n-1} = k) \quad (14)$$

with the cumulative distribution function $F_{kl}(w)$:

$$F_{kl}(w) = \Pr(H_n \leq w | Z_{n-1} = k, Z_n = l), \quad w \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

where $H_n = W_n - W_{n-1}$. As already defined in the semi-Markov process Y_w , can be built via pairs $\{Z_n, W_n\}_{n \geq 0}$, from the state and the respective jump times. The parameters underlying this formation involve the embedded chain transition probability, p_{kl} presented in the Equation (14), as well as its distribution from the sojourn time for each transition $k \rightarrow l$, presented in the Equation (15).

Embedded chain transition probabilities are often arranged in a stochastic matrix, $P = [p_{kl}]$ (where $p_{kk} = 0$ is set). Furthermore, assuming the sojourn time distribution is continuous, this distribution is often represented in different forms, including density, survival, or hazard functions.

The density function of the sojourn time is

$$f_{kl}(w) = \lim_{\Delta w \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Pr(H_n \in (w, w + \Delta w) | Z_{n-1} = k, Z_n = l)}{\Delta w} \quad (16)$$

The survival function that corresponds to this is

$$S_{kl}(w) = \Pr(H_n > w | Z_{n-1} = k, Z_n = l) = 1 - F_{kl}(w) \quad (17)$$

($S_{kl}(w)$ is a descending function, where $S_{kl}(0) = 1$ and $\lim_{w \rightarrow +\infty} S_{kl}(w) = 0$).

If there are two states, namely k and l , the hazard function, which is frequently thought of as the probability of a transition happening at a particular period $(w, w + \Delta w)$ without any transition before the time w , is written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{kl}(t) &= \lim_{\Delta w \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Pr(H_n \in (w, w + \Delta w) | Z_{n-1} = k, Z_n = l, H_n > w)}{\Delta w} \\ &= \lim_{\Delta w \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Pr(H_n \in (w, w + \Delta w) | Z_{n-1} = k, Z_n = l)}{\Delta w \Pr(H_n > w | Z_{n-1} = k, Z_n = l)} \\ &= \frac{f_{kl}(w)}{S_{kl}(w)} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

The survival function of the sojourn time in state k before transitioning to state l is written as

$$S_{kl}(t) = \Pr(H_n > w | Z_{n-1} = k, Z_n = l)$$

So to show the survival function of the sojourn time in state k at time, w can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} S_k(w) &= \Pr(H_n > w | Z_{n-1} = k) \\ &= \Pr(Z_n = l | Z_{n-1} = k) \frac{\Pr(H_n > w | Z_{n-1} = k)}{\Pr(Z_n = l | Z_{n-1} = k)} \\ &= \Pr(Z_n = l | Z_{n-1} = k) \Pr(H_n > w | Z_{n-1} = k, Z_n = l) \\ &= p_{kl} S_{kl}(w) \\ &= \sum_{k \neq l} p_{kl} S_{kl}(w) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

The density function of each distribution used for continuous-time is presented as follows (Ross, 2007).

1. Weibull Distribution ($Y \sim \text{WEI}(y; \lambda, d)$)

$$f(y) = \begin{cases} \frac{d}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y}{\lambda}\right)^{d-1} e^{-\left(\frac{y}{\lambda}\right)^d}, & y > 0 \\ 0, & y \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

If $d < 1$ the monotonic hazard level goes down; if $d = 1$ the hazard level is constant (Exponential distribution), and if $d > 1$ the monotonic hazard level increases [?].

2. Exponential Distribution ($Y \sim \text{EXP}(y; \lambda)$)

$$f(y) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\lambda} e^{-\frac{1}{\lambda}y}, & y > 0 \\ 0, & y \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Exponential Distribution of Sojourn Time

Equation (21) can be used to determine the survival function and the hazard function of the Exponential distribution as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} S_{kl}(w) &= 1 - F_{kl}(w) \\ &= 1 - \int_0^w f_{kl}(y) dy \\ &= 1 - \int_0^w \frac{1}{\lambda} e^{-\frac{1}{\lambda}y} dw \\ &= 1 - \left(e^{-\frac{1}{\lambda}y} \Big|_0^w \right) \\ &= e^{-\frac{1}{\lambda}w} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

So we can also get the hazard function from the following Exponential distribution.

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{ij}(w) &= \frac{f_{ij}(w)}{S_{ij}(w)} \\ &= \frac{\frac{1}{\lambda} e^{-\frac{1}{\lambda}w}}{e^{-\frac{1}{\lambda}w}} \\ &= \frac{1}{\lambda} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Weibull Distribution of Sojourn Time

Equation (20) can be used to determine the survival and hazard functions of the Weibull distribution where the scale and shape parameters for the transition from k to l are λ_{kl} and η_{kl} , is obtained as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} S_{kl}(w) &= 1 - F_{kl}(w) \\ &= 1 - \int_0^w f_{ij}(y) dy \\ &= 1 - \int_0^w \frac{\eta}{\lambda} \left(\frac{y}{\lambda} \right)^{\eta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{y}{\lambda} \right)^\eta} dy \\ &= 1 - \int_0^w \frac{\eta \left(\frac{y}{\lambda} \right)^{\eta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{y}{\lambda} \right)^\eta}}{\lambda} dy \\ &= 1 - \int_0^w \frac{\eta y^{\eta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{y}{\lambda} \right)^\eta}}{\lambda^\eta} dy \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

to do $\int_0^w \frac{\eta y^{\eta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{y}{\lambda} \right)^\eta}}{\lambda^\eta} dy$, for example $u = -\frac{y^\eta}{\lambda^\eta}$, then $\frac{du}{dy} = -\frac{\eta y^{\eta-1}}{\lambda^\eta}$ atau $dy = -\frac{\lambda^\eta y^{1-\eta}}{\eta} du$ so that the following results are obtained.

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^w e^{-\left(\frac{y}{\lambda}\right)^\eta \frac{\eta y^{\eta-1}}{\lambda^\eta}} dy &= \int_0^w e^{-u} \frac{\eta y^{\eta-1}}{\lambda^\eta} \left(-\frac{\lambda^\eta y^{1-\eta}}{\eta} du\right) \\ &= -\int_0^w e^{-u} du \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Equation (25) can be substituted for the survival function in equation (24) to obtain the following form.

$$\begin{aligned} S_{kl}(w) &= 1 - \int_0^w \frac{\eta y^{\eta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{y}{\lambda}\right)^\eta}}{\lambda^\eta} dy \\ &= 1 - \int_0^w e^{-u} du \\ &= 1 + e^{-u} \Big|_0^w \\ &= 1 + \left(e^{\left(\frac{w}{\lambda}\right)^\eta} - 1\right) \\ &= e^{-\left(\frac{w}{\lambda}\right)^\eta} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

So that the hazard function can also be obtained from the following Weibull distribution.

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{kl}(w) &= \frac{f_{kl}(w)}{S_{kl}(w)} \\ &= \frac{\frac{\eta}{\lambda} \left(\frac{w}{\lambda}\right)^{\eta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{w}{\lambda}\right)^\eta}}{e^{-\left(\frac{w}{\lambda}\right)^\eta}} \\ &= \frac{\eta}{\lambda} \left(\frac{w}{\lambda}\right)^{\eta-1} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Application of the SIRD Epidemic Model to the spread of COVID-19

The SIRD epidemic model uses four states, susceptible, infected, recovered, and deceased, with transitions as shown in Figure 1. The data used is COVID-19 case data in the Special Region of Yogyakarta (DIY), Indonesia, from March 15, 2020, to July 31, 2020. Explanation of each state in Figure 1 is a susceptible state (**S**) consists of people who are susceptible to COVID-19 during the study period, the infected state (**I**) consists of people who are confirmed positive for COVID-19, the recovered state (**R**) consists of people who recover from COVID -19 after conducting two SWAB tests with negative results, and the deceased state (**D**) consists of people who died from COVID-19.

Furthermore, each distribution of sojourn time in the Markov model uses the Exponential distribution, while for semi-Markov uses the Weibull distribution. A comparison of the two models can be seen in Table 1. Tabel 1 shows the best model used to make predictions from the value of *Akaike information criteria* (AIC), which is a semi-Markov model with a Weibull distribution of sojourn time.

Table 1
AIC Value of Each Continuous Time Model.

Model	Distribution	AIC
Markov	Exponential	13521.47
Semi-Markov	Weibull	12703.31

Note: derived from research.

Conclusions

The SIRD epidemic model, which consists of four states, susceptible, infected, recovered, and deceased, can be used to model the spread of infectious diseases. The maximum likelihood method can obtain transition parameter estimation with Markov assumptions. The SIRD epidemic model with a semi-Markov assumption can overcome the weaknesses of the Markov assumption. So to model the spread of infectious diseases, it is better to pay attention to the sojourn time in one state before transitioning to another state. The sojourn time is exponentially distributed for the Markov model, while the sojourn time is a Weibull distribution for the semi-Markov model. The results of a comparison of the two models found that the semi-Markov model was better than the Markov model for COVID-19 cases in DIY, Indonesia. This can be seen from the AIC value of the semi-Markov model, which is smaller than the Markov model.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Author contribution statement

All the authors declare that the final version of this paper was read and approved.

The total contribution percentage for the conceptualization, preparation, and correction of this paper was as follows: M.C.D. 40 %., Y.M.L. 30 % and D.F.R. 30 %.

Data availability statement

The data supporting the results of this study will be made available by the corresponding author, [F.Z], upon reasonable request.

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